

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TRADITIONAL VS HYBRID CLASSES: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LEARNING OUTCOMES

Shivangi Verma

Assistant Professor

Ramanand Institute of Pharmacy and Management, Haridwar, Uttarakhand

Email: shivangiverma221@gmail.com, 9045384593

Manuj Uniyal

Assistant Professor

Ramanand Institute of Pharmacy and Management, Haridwar, Uttarakhand

Email: Manujcopy.ksu@gmail.com, 9808599035

Abstract

The Artificial Intelligence in Smart Classes and traditional classes is a help in teaching Skills. This is a deep learning skills which enhances the difference teaching styles. It is proposed to outline the present or future quality of study material. This paper we discuss the concept of Artificial Intelligence in teaching classes vs hybrid classes. In this study, primary data collected from student of B.com 1st year, 2nd Year and 3rd Year. Data collected through structural questionnaire. The number of respondent in this study 250, which is collected. Simple random sampling were used to collect the data in study area . It is found from the analysis that 75 students agree with traditional method but 78 students can says that they are neutral with this method. From the study reveal that 98 students are agree with modern method and 83 students can responses are neutral. The study concluded that a comparative study consistently show that artificial intelligence offers significant advantages in education sector, primarily through by personalization and give immediately feedback as soon as possible which traditional and hybrid methods are struggle to provide motivation and engagement, also provide efficiency. We find flexibility, traditional strengths.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Teaching Styles, Personalization, Awareness, Hybrid Classes, Active Learning.

Introduction

In an artificial intelligence is used in hospitals, education sector, IT sector. In education sector we have use Artificial Intelligence elaborate the learning outcomes as well as learner centered pedagogical practice refer to teaching methods that focus on the needs, abilities, interests and teaching styles of students, awareness rather than just delivering content from the teacher's. In traditional classes, It is a physical classrooms. They focus on exams, assessment and other activities. Artificial Intelligence methods use Hybrid technologies for Hybrid Classes. It can be utilized the Artificial Intelligence tools for much more better teaching skills. Artificial Intelligence focuses on teaching styles to improve the quality of teaching. It helps to students' and teacher's. In traditional classes, we have to take physical classes in the classrooms, maintained attendance register and discipline in the classrooms. But in Hybrid Classes in Artificial Intelligence, we have utilize the tools of Artificial Intelligence like ChatGpt, Deepseek, Perplexity, etc. Teachers' and Students both of them utilize these types of Artificial Intelligence Tools for learning skills and Personalization. Teacher's can be use the Smart TV for more effective modern classes. With the help of structured diagram measure the awareness level of among students.

STRUCTURAL DIAGRAM OF LEARNING

Sources: Prepared By Author

Learning:- Learning is skills, experience, study, values. It is behaviors through by practice. They related to knowledge and development our skills.

Traditional Method:- In this method, we can use black board to enhance the learning skills. Black Board is a large and short board with a smooth dark surface area and they attached to a wall or it can be supported used by teachers in colleges for writing on with marker or chalk.

Modern Method:-In this method, We can use the artificial intelligence learning skills. It is ability to enhance the learning skills like problem solving, language understating, learning process, easy data collection, exam preparation, presentation also. It can be utilize the artificial intelligence tools like ChatGpt, Deepseek, etc.

Literature Review

TanveerBaig (2025),This paper, we study about adaptive pedagogy with focus on the challenges and future potential of the technology by educators. It is economical, technological and learning abilities.

Changyi Li & Jiang Long(2025),In this research paper, It can be focusing on teaching styles through by artificial intelligence. They improve learning knowledge for the students bright future. It is utilize the artificial intelligence tools to improve knowledge.

Ananth Hariharan (2025),This paper, we can study about pedagogical techniques of traditional classrooms the enhanced education system. It is develop more effective and learning enlivenment. Students deserve high quality education.

Susan Rochelle &Dr. Sushith (2024), In this research paper, we can says that education is a part of students learning skills. It is compare between traditional and modern learning in teaching skills. Artificial Intelligence and Traditional Methods can identify the educator benefits and its more challenges and future directions also.

Mario Ayala- Pazmino (2023),This research paper, It is connect with AI – education has generated with significance educators improve teaching and learning skills. AI tools can be reduce the teacher planning time by administrative task and they focus on more practical teaching activities.

Objectives

- To determine the awareness level among Artificial Intelligence in Modern Learning Outcomes.
- To compare traditional and modern method of learning.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is the systematic plan for conducting research, which includes the specific procedures, techniques, and reasoning used to collect, analyze, and interpret data.

In this study, Data collected from the secondary sources such as articles, research paper, report, journal, website etc. Collected data were reviewed and analyze with help of compression traditional study and modern. It is Quantitative analysis. The time period of study august 2025 to November 2025.

In this study, primary data collected from student of B.com 1st year, 2nd Year and 3rd Year. Data collected through structural questionnaire. The number of respondent in this study 250, which is collected from the Ramanand Institute of Pharmacy and Management in Haridwar, Uttarakhand. Simple random sampling were used to collect the data in study area. After collecting data, analysis with the help of statistical tool as percentage method and graphical representation. 5 point Likert scale were applied in the study as strongly disagree, disagree, agree, natural, strongly agree.

Data Analysis

Table 1 Demographic Profile of Respondent

Students	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Boy's	160	64
Girl's	90	36
Total	250	100

Sources: Author's Primary Data Collection

Graph 1

Interpretation: This is demographic profile table and they identify the students like girls and boys. We have total number of respondent 250 ,Boys give 160 respondent and girls give 90 respondent.

Table 2 Age Group of Respondent

Age Group	No. of Respondent	Percentage
18 to 20	70	28
20 to 22	85	34
Above 22	95	38
Total	250	100

Sources: Author's Primary Data Collection

Graph 2

Interpretation: In this table, we can show the age group like 18 to 20 age group gives 70 respondent, 20 to 22 age group gives 85 respondent(highest) and above 22 age group gives 95 respondent.

Table 3 Satisfaction about Traditional Learning

Question	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Yes	153	61.2
No	97	38.8
Total	250	100

Sources: Author's Primary Data Collection

Graph 3

Interpretation: In this graph, It is traditional method utilize in learning skills. Students give respondent like some students says that it is good for learning = 153 and some students are not comfortable with traditional method gives 97 respondent.

Table 4 Effectiveness Level of Traditional Learning

Statement	S.D	D	N	A	S.A	Total	%
Traditional Learning Effective in Present Education System	13 (5.2)	68(27.2)	78(31.2)	75(30)	16(6.4)	250	100

Sources: Author Primary Data Compilation, S.D = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Neutral, A = Agree, S.A = Strongly Agree

Graph 4

Interpretation: In this table, We found the students respondent of traditional method. We finds 75 students agree with traditional method but 78 students can says that they are neutral with this method.

Table 5 Awareness about Modern Learning

Question	No. of Respondent	Percentage
Yes	187	74.8
No	63	25.2
Total	250	100

Sources: Author's Primary Data Collection

Interpretation: In modern method, Highest respondent of students= 187. Student's aware about modern technology. But 63 student's are not want to aware about modern technology as well as learning.

Graph 5

Table 6 Effectiveness Level of Modern Learning

Statement	S.D	D	N	A	S.A	Total	%
Modern Learning helpful in Present Education System	9(3.6)	17(6.8)	83(33.2)	98(39.2)	43(17.2)	250	100

Sources: Author Primary Data Compilation, S.D = Strongly Disagree, D = Disagree, N = Not Agree, A = Agree, S.A = Strongly Agree

Graph 6

Interpretation: In this method, 98 students are agree with modern method. 83 students can says that they are neutral with this method.

Findings

1. It is demographic profile. In this graph, maximum respondent of boy's 160. Age group table identify the above 22 years is the highest respondent 98.
2. Student's awareness about the new method of learning i.e. ChatGPT and Deepseek, from the study it is found that 75% the B.com student's of Ramanand Institute of Pharmacy and Management College having awareness is about and 25% student's are not aware about it. It is

because of student having smart phone, lack of knowledge about modern method or be student belong to backward family or rural areas.

3. Student's awareness about the new method of learning i.e. ChatGPT and Deepseek, from the study it is found that 61.2% the B.com student's of Ramanand Institute of Pharmacy and Management College having awareness is about and 38.8% student's are not aware about it. It is because of student having smart phone, lack of knowledge about traditional method or be student belong to backward family or rural areas.

4. 75% student's agree to conduct traditional continuous but 78% student's are neutral. No response both of them.

5. 98% students make learning adopt and 43% students are strongly agree.

Conclusion

It is concluded from the study that artificial intelligence in traditional classes vs hybrid classes: a comparative study learning outcomes. We can enhance the quality of teaching skills through by modern method as well as hybrid classes. It helps to students' and teacher's. In traditional classes, we have to take physical classes in the classrooms, maintained attendance register and discipline in the classrooms. But in Hybrid Classes in Artificial Intelligence, we have utilize the tools of Artificial Intelligence like ChatGpt, Deepseek, Perplexity, etc. Teachers' and students both of them utilize these types of Artificial Intelligence Tools for learning skills and Personalization. We are help of teacher's enhance the knowledge of learning skills thought by workshop, webinar, faculty development program in our institute for student's bright future.

Suggestion

- In college's, we give suggest modern and traditional continuity.
- They are provide Modern knowledge of the teacher's.
- We can conduct workshop, faculty development program, webinar in the college's to enhance the quality of teaching skills.

References

TanveerBaig (2025), "the Impoact of artificial Intelligence on Adaptive Learning: A Comprative Study of Tradtional and AI- Based Pedagogies", Dialogue Social

Science Review, ISSN Online: 3007-3154, ISSN Print: 3007-3146, Vol.3, No.3, March 2025,
www.thedssr.com

Changyi Li & Jiang Long (2025) “Comparing AI- Assisted and Traditional Teaching in College English: Pedagogical Benefits and Learning Behaviors”, MDPI, Volume 16, Issue 10,
<https://doi.org/10.3390/info16100895>

AnanthHariharan (2025), “Artificial Intelligence for Optimal Learning: A Comparative Approach towards AI – enhanced Learning Environments”, ARXIV, 12 Oct 2025,
[arXiv:2510.11755v1](https://arxiv.org/html/2510.11755v1), <https://arxiv.org/html/2510.11755v1>

Susan Rochelle & Dr. Sushith (2024), “Exploring the AI Era: A Comparative Analysis of AI – Driven Education and Traditional Teaching Methods”, International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR), ISSN: 2582-2160, Volume 6, Issue 4, July- August 2024,
www.ijfmr.com

Mario Ayala- Pazmino (2023), “Artificial Intelligence in Education: Exploring the Potential Benefits and Risks”, Research Gate, V8-N3 (May-June)2023, pp. 892-899,
<https://doi.org/10.33386/593dp.2023.3.1827>

<https://www.imdv.com/name/nm5296429>

Research Methodology: Methods and Techniques” by Kothari and Garg, and “Research Methodology: A Step-by-step Guide for Beginners” by Ranjit Kumar.

<https://www.avadolearning.com>

<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>

<https://www.un.org>